

Analysis of organizational and economic indicators of innovative activity of enterprises producing spare parts for the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Tashkent State Technical University,
Senior lecturer of the department
Internal Combustion Engines,
Refrigeration and Cryogenic
Technology.
Kurbanov Abdulaziz Muzafarovich,
qurbonovabdulaziz8913@gmail.com
tel:(90)000-98-58

Annotation

The article analyzes the organizational and economic indicators of innovative activity of enterprises producing spare parts for the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the results of 2023 and the business plan for 2024.

Keywords: automotive industry, spare parts, manufacturing, innovation, economic efficiency, technological innovation,

Introduction

The automotive industry occupies one of the leading positions in the economy of Uzbekistan. Production volumes are growing from year to year, with more than 370,000 vehicles produced last year in 2023. In the strategy “Uzbekistan-2030” is tasked with creating a competitive environment in the automotive industry and increasing production to 1 million units. Currently, the automobile industry of Uzbekistan ranks 26th among the countries that produce motor vehicles, and therefore in the CIS area it ranks second after the Russian automobile industry and first among the countries of Central Asia in this indicator. Uzbekistan has been a member of the International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers since 1998 [1].

Currently, the number of local Uzbek enterprises for the production of spare parts is more than 300 (including 26 industry-specific, 280 private). The automobile cluster is located mainly in the valley. Samarkand region produces trucks and buses, while Jizzakh region produces passenger commercial vehicles. The network enterprises employ and employ more than 200,000 people.

In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4397 “on additional measures for accelerated development of the automotive

industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan“ in 2020, “Uzavtosanoat” JSC together with the international consulting company Boston Consulting Group presented the strategy of the automotive industry for the period up to 2030 [2].

In accordance with this Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-300 dated September 12, 2023 “On measures for high-quality and timely implementation of the Strategy “Uzbekistan-2030” in 2023 , the approval of the program for the development of the automotive industry until 2030, taking into account the following goals, is marked with a sign:

- Creating a competitive environment in the automotive industry and bringing production volumes to 1 million units, including the production of 300 thousand electric vehicles per year;

- Bringing the level of localization of components and necessary spare parts for passenger cars, agricultural machinery and automobiles to 60% and widely attracting investors to this.

Materials

Having developed a draft resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further develop the competitive environment and increase investment attractiveness in the automotive industry of the Republic” to create equal conditions for companies operating in the automotive industry and those wishing to start operating in the automotive industry of the Republic a decision was made to submit and take measures to the relevant ministries and departments. The automotive industry is characterized by incentives that determine equal business conditions and are determined by the level of localization, effective application of innovations in technological processes that meet the requirements of “industrial assembly”. Thus, equal conditions will be created for all applicants working in the automotive industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Continuation of practical work on bringing the production capacity of JSC “UzAutoMotors” and localization of enterprises to 500 thousand cars. It is also planned to continue the work started to increase the level of localization of existing models, organize work on the production of components for new models at domestic enterprises and the development of new components, organizational and economic organization of innovative activities in production. At the same time, in the course of 2024:

- Casting of the internal combustion engine cylinder block part CSS Prime;

- Production of “Rear axle” components for new car models;

- Production of generators for new car models;

- In addition, in exchange for cooperation with other companies:

- Production of tires for Damas and new car models;

Localization of seat fabrics and PVC materials for Damas, Cobalt and new car models. Improving the efficiency of activity, efficiency of innovative activity of enterprises of JSC “Uzavtosanoat” stabilization and further improvement of their financial condition. The system provides suggestions for reforming (transforming) the management model, including changing the organizational structures of the central office and enterprises using foreign experience. At the same time, it is planned to involve experienced, specialized and/or highly qualified specialists in the enterprise management processes, as well as introduce innovations into production. This is expected to be achieved by reducing costs/cost savings by improving operational efficiency by optimizing fixed costs associated with production, by transferring imported products to alternative suppliers and increasing production volumes. Search for alternative suppliers of raw materials and optimize the costs of industrial enterprises of “Uzavtosanoat” JSC for the purchase of imported raw materials. In order to expand the geography of production of automobiles and agricultural machinery, as well as increase export volumes, continue work on organizing production facilities for the production of cars and machinery produced by the company, based on SKD and CKD technology in neighboring countries. JV LLC “BYD Uzbekistan Factory” in the second half of 2024 will launch the project “Organization of production of cars on new energy sources”, and by the end of the year it is planned to produce 10 thousand electric and hybrid cars BYD. Initially, it was planned to release the Song Plus and Chazor models. Continue and complete the work that has been started to improve the localization level of existing models, organize work on timely, according to schedules, production of components for new models at domestic enterprises. In the newly created industrial center, work continues on the placement of new enterprises for the production of components and the implementation of projects. Continue work on establishing the activities of the “benchmarking center” under JSC “UzAutoMotors”. Digitize specific data collection processes by gradually implementing the ALP resource management system in 3 large localization businesses.

Optimization of inventory balances and acceleration of TMB turnover at the chain's enterprises through regular implementation of the following measures:

- transfer of monthly orders to weekly ones;
- efficient use of container capacity;
- consolidation of small cargo volumes;
- reduction of cargo transit time by choosing optimal routes;
- inventory optimization in warehouses.

Implementation of innovative projects by enterprises of the company's system, the implementation of which is scheduled for 2024 by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 307 of July 6, 2022.

Today, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 “On the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” on measures to bring the sphere of information and communication technologies to a new level in 2022-2023 within the framework of the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 strategy, as well as in accordance with the new stage in the field of In order to implement the priority tasks for export at 2 enterprises of the “Uzavtosanoat” system, a project is being implemented to introduce an ixp system in “UzTong Hong Company” LLC and “Auto Climate Control” LLC, the purpose of which is to automate the enterprise's production processes, reduce the human factor and digitalize business processes. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan On measures to improve the coverage and quality of digital services and digital transformation of industries, industries and territories PC-162 defines the task for implementing the following projects:

1. Automation of the processes of movement and accounting of containers on the territory of the enterprise in JSC “UzAutoMotors”. According to this task, the programmers of “UzAutoMotors” JSC are developing a program.

2. “UzAutoMotorsPowertrain” JSC is working on the implementation of the DLP system to prevent data leakage. In order to automate the processes of online booking and sale of passenger cars produced by “UzAutoMotors” JSC, as well as to ensure transparency in the sale of cars, it is planned to develop a new system, and currently work is underway to modernize the online sales system. Introduction of an online registration system for stopping processes on the line that occur in the assembly shop of “UzAutoMotors” JSC. This system is aimed at implementing projects to develop the line Stop program in order to reduce the human factor in the process of stopping lines, timely (online) providing management with information related to stopping lines.

“UzAvtoMotors” JSC is constantly working to improve the dealer network of the domestic market. A new concept and requirements for the development of the dealer network, optimization of dealerships and opening categories of dealerships were approved. Dealerships were re-equipped in accordance with the standard of the Chevrolet D-2 brand. From 2023, delivery of a new model of the Onix car on the Gem platform began to customers. It is also planned to increase sales of Malibu, Equinox, Tahoe and Traverse cars. Also, from 2023, sales of the Chevrolet Malibu car will start in a complete set equipped with new modern security equipment. From the 4th quarter of 2023, sales of the new Chevrolet Captiva car began. It is expected that more competitors will appear in the B/C sedan and A/B / C hatchback segments. This type of competition increases competition in the mass segment. In order to maintain market share in the B-segment (the mass segment in Uzbekistan), in 2024-2025, it is planned to upgrade the affordable Cobalt sedan. The introduction of the

Face&Tail elevator, as well as the addition of multimedia system control buttons on the steering wheel, heated seats, updating the dashboard, multimedia system and enriching the vehicle's equipment with a rear-view camera from the factory. Face-Lift and tail-Lift not only update the appearance, but also improve the current characteristics of the car (aerodynamics and appearance from the inside of the car). JV "BYD Uzbekistan" LLC will start operating 9 official dealerships in 2023, the sale of BYD Song Plus, Chazor, Han cars will be established, and by the end of the year it is expected to sell 10 thousand cars. Sales of products of JV "SamAvto" LLC in the domestic market are carried out by 35 dealer enterprises located throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan. In order to meet the needs of consumers, there are 3 territorial warehouses in the republic (in Tashkent, Urgench and Ferghana regions), which are equipped with a system and special racks recommended by Isuzu (Japan). At the plant of JV LLC "SamAvto", in a specially equipped training center on the territory of the Samarkand Automobile College and in the center for professional training in the city of Samarkand (the center was created in cooperation with KOICA), specialists of JV LLC "SamAvto" conduct training and advanced training of personnel for dealerships. Every year, technical competitions are held among car service technicians of authorized service stations, during which the best technical specialists are identified and experience is exchanged in the field of car maintenance. The winners of the competition can participate in the international Auto Mechanics Competition in Japan. In addition, the company holds various events and promotions to attract customers. When carrying out actions, the support of Japanese specialists who monitor compliance with maintenance standards is used.

Activities in export markets

"UzAvtoMotors" JSC has been exporting cars to the CIS and African countries under the Chevrolet brand since March 2020. Currently, all foreign dealer networks have switched to the Chevrolet network. It is planned to reduce the cost of production and thus continue work on regulating export prices. In particular, it is planned to continue exporting in the form of SKD kits Chevrolet Malibu, Chevrolet Damas/Labo, Chevrolet Cobalt, Chevrolet Tracker, Chevrolet Tahoe, Chevrolet Traverse, Chevrolet Equinox, supplied to "SaryarkaAvtoProm" (Kazakhstan). In 2023, "SaryarkaAvtoProm" (Kazakhstan) launched production of a new CKD-style Onix car. Along with the Chevrolet Cobalt, Chevrolet Damas/Labo, Chevrolet Malibu, Chevrolet Tracker, Chevrolet Lacetti, Chevrolet Equinox, Chevrolet Tahoe, and Chevrolet Traverse cars exported as SKD kits, the production facilities of Azer mash CP LLC (Republic of Azerbaijan) were used to assemble and sell the car on the market. As a result of the work on opening new export markets in 2022, cooperation was established with the IMPEX enterprise in the Lebanese state. As a result, Spark cars were exported to this country. The prospects for exporting Cobalt

cars to this country were also studied. In addition, negotiations were held with GM Corporation and local enterprises in the region to establish exports to the Middle East and Africa. In 2023, a new dealership opened in the Armenian market and sales began. In 2024, it is planned to assemble and sell SKD-style passenger cars in the Kyrgyz Republic. In 2024, it is planned to start exporting Cobalt and Tracker cars to Mongolia. In 2024, it is planned to start exporting Cobalt, Onix and Tracker cars to Georgia. In 2024, it is planned to produce and sell a new Chevrolet Captiva car in the SKD style in Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan. Finished products and components produced by enterprises that study market trends and localization are also planned to participate in international automobile exhibitions and presentations in order to increase sales. In order to provide after-sales services, the company will continue to supply spare parts to distributors in foreign markets. The results of operations in the export markets and a full analysis of the situation in the markets are attached. JV “BYD Uzbekistan” LLC is currently negotiating the opening of dealerships in the Republics of Tajikistan, Azerbaijan and Georgia. JV “SamAvto” LLC plans to export truck chassis and bus components SAZ HD50 for production in the territory of “Azermash Park” LLC from 2021. Two trucks and 1 bus were exported to the Republic of Moldova. It is also planned to ship 2 more trucks by the end of 2023. In 2023, “SamAuto” introduced a new generation of Isuzu pickups, which will allow them to compete with other leading pickup truck manufacturers in export markets. In 2023, it is planned to establish exports to Mongolia and Moldova, and in 2024 it is planned to increase exports to these countries. In 2024, the Kyrgyz Republic will begin assembling and selling commercial vehicles in the SKD style. In 2024, industry enterprises of the industry plan to export auto parts to the conveyors of foreign automakers, including: the export of taillights for the Berlingo model is planned for 2024 by the Uzchasis joint venture at the PSMA Rus and PsaAuto SA enterprises in France.

Discussion

Innovative activity of enterprises producing spare parts for the automotive industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on specific organizational and economic indicators. The analysis of these indicators is important for the effective establishment of innovative development of enterprises, increasing their competitiveness and achieving overall economic efficiency. The following are the main indicators that you can pay attention to when evaluating innovation:

1. Indicators of investment activity and appropriations

- Volume of investment in innovation: the funds allocated for innovation projects show how much attention enterprises pay to the introduction of technological innovations. The higher this indicator is, the more funds the company spends on new technologies and production processes.

- Financial support and government subsidies: Government subsidies and benefits are important to support innovation. This requires the Government of Uzbekistan to implement a policy of financial support for innovative programs.
2. Indicators of production of innovative products
 - Type and share of new products: the share of new or improved products in relation to the total output indicates the effectiveness of innovation activities. If this indicator is high, it reflects the result of innovative development.
 - Export indicators and share of export-oriented innovative products: export volumes and their share in total production show the potential of an enterprise to enter the international market. Export of innovative products serves to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise in international markets.
 3. Labor force and personnel qualification indicators
 - Share of employees involved in innovation projects and research: the participation of qualified employees in innovation activities is important. The level of training, retraining and advanced training increases the innovative potential of the enterprise.
 - Personnel involvement in research activities: the number of employees involved in research and experimental work at the enterprise is an important factor in the implementation of innovative projects and ideas.
 4. Economic efficiency indicators
 - Profitability and profitability: indicators of profit and profitability obtained as a result of innovation activities help to assess the economic efficiency of the enterprise. These indicators reflect how successfully the company has invested in innovation.
 - Production efficiency and cost reduction: reducing production costs and improving resource efficiency through innovation contributes to improved economic outcomes. New technologies and processes increase efficiency and improve product quality.
 5. Technological and infrastructure indicators
 - Level of digitization: digitization of production processes, the level of automation and the use of modern technologies contribute to increasing the level of innovative development of enterprises.
 - Upgrading the infrastructure and technological base: upgrading the infrastructure necessary for innovation, purchasing new equipment and automating production processes are among the main factors for improving the efficiency of the enterprise.
 6. Environmental performance indicators

- Environmental impact indicators: reducing emissions, meeting environmental requirements, and improving energy efficiency through innovative processes are important indicators for achieving environmental sustainability in the automotive industry.
- Recycling and utilization of resources: by recycling raw materials and resources using innovative approaches, their reuse increases efficiency and makes the production process more environmentally sustainable.

Based on these indicators, the innovative activities of enterprises producing spare parts for the automotive industry in Uzbekistan will be analyzed and the possibility of developing effective innovation strategies for them will be increased.

List of references:

1. Fundamentals of innovative activity development at industrial enterprises. Kurbanov A.M. "Industrial economy and management: problems and solutions" Tashkent-2024. 154-156.

2. Appendix to the Minutes of the Supervisory Board of "Uzavtosanoat" JSC No. 18-2023 dated November 30, 2023. Tashkent – 2023.